

Design of Ergonomic Flour Dough Mixer with Participatory Approach to Increase Work Productivity MSME Employees

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ABSTRACT:

Culinary businesses that are members of MSMEs usually process foodstuffs, including stirring flour dough manually using their hands. It is ineffective, makes you tired quickly, and takes a long time. Usually there are complaints such as complaints of arm muscles, complaints of fatigue in the hands, pain in the palms, and it takes a long time, resulting in subpar worker productivity. Consequently, a participation flour dough mixer that is ergonomic is required. In order to conduct this research, an experimental design of a flour dough mixer was created and applied to sixteen samples of MSME employees in the Tabanan Regency. The Nordic Body Map questionnaire was used to measure musculoskeletal diseases, and the workload was divided by the survey results to determine job productivity. The employee's work pulse was measured using a pulse meter. The findings demonstrated that the ergonomic flour dough mixer was designed based on the worker's anthropometric measurements. The tool's height was matched to the worker's standing elbow height, and the container's dimensions matched the worker's hand's reach. The design of an ergonomic flour dough mixer can reduce the workload of MSME employees by 15.1%; reduce musculoskeletal disorders of MSME employees by 47.9%; reduce MSME employee fatigue by 52.3%; and increase the work productivity of MSME employees by 501.1%.

Keywords: flour dough mixer, ergonomics, work productivity.

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INTRODUCTION

Micro, small, and medium-sized firms, or MSMEs, are a significant component of the Indonesian economy. Small industry has a lot of issues that need to be resolved. [1], [2]. Using relevant technology, or the application of appropriate technology, is one way to find a solution [3], [4], [5]. The participatory principle dictates that the technology used should be user-oriented to ensure safe, comfortable, and productive use by users. This is compliant with ergonomic guidelines [6], [7], [8]. The appropriate technology tool, which is designed as a flour dough mixer, is one of the tools that can be a solution to the problems of MSMEs in Tabanan district or elsewhere in terms of stirring flour dough as a food ingredient, such as making dough for bread, fried bananas, meatballs, noodles, and others.

The employees' early complaints and suggestions for engagement indicate that they get fatigued easily and could use a stirring tool. In order for this equipment to be used efficiently, safely, comfortably, and to boost work productivity in line with the expectations of MSME entrepreneurs and their staff, it must also be customised to the user's anthropometry. The purpose of this study is to

make an ergonomic flour dough mixer design and to measure the increase in employee work productivity from the use of ergonomic flour dough mixer design compared to the previous method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed an experimental design with a group receiving the same treatment (same subject) [9]. There is time washing out between the two treatment groups [9], [10]. The following chart provides an illustration of the research design.

Figure 1. Research Chart

Information:

P = population

RS = simple random

S = sample

P1 = treatment 1 (using the old method/manual stirring)

P2 = treatment 2 (stirring the dough using the design of the mixer)

WO = Washing Out for two days

O1 and O3 showed data collection carried out before work (pre-test), on: Frequency of resting pulse of the research subjects.

O2 and O4 show that data collection is carried out after work (post-test), against:

1. Working pulse frequency, shortly after working.
2. calculation of fatigue, muscle complaints, and work productivity.

The variables in this study were workload, musculoskeletal disorders, work fatigue, and work productivity. The Nordic Body Map questionnaire was used to measure musculoskeletal diseases, the employee's work pulse was used to calculate workload, and the workload was divided by the stir result to determine work productivity.

The data were analyzed descriptively to provide a descriptive description of all the research data stated in the form of frequency, average, standard deviation, percentage change from pulse data, fatigue, MSD complaints, fatigue, and productivity. The data normality test was carried out to see the distribution of data for each group using the Shapiro Wilk test on pulse rate data, MSD complaints, fatigue, and productivity. The test was conducted between the groups in the control group and the treatment group, where the test used t-pairs at a 95% significance level.

RESULTS

Assembly and Specifications of the Appliance

The process of making the design of this ergonomic flour dough mixer has several stages. The first stage is the creation of engineering drawings to suit the expected needs with frame dimensions that are in accordance with the user's anthropometry. Next is the selection of materials, assembly, and finishing in the form of painting.

This ergonomic flour dough mixer uses an electric motor drive. The specifications of the tool are as follows:

Figure 2. Flour Dough Mixer Machine Specifications

Information:

1. Frame.
2. Electric motor.
3. Pulley cover/V belt.
4. Flour dough holder
5. Bearing.
6. Slows Power.

Specification:

- a) Electric power: 1.1 KW
- b) Electrical voltage: 220 volts
- c) Machine container capacity: 15 kg
- d) Rotation speed: 40 RPM
- e) Receptacle Material: full stainless steel

It also uses a pulley and a V-belt to reduce the rotation of the mixer. For the safety of the wearer, the drive system (pulleys and V-belts) is equipped with a cover plate. The rotation can be set with a control switch, it can be in the right or left direction.

Subject Anthropometric Measurements

The anthropometric measurement of the subject was carried out as the basis for making the frame design of the ergonomic flour dough mixer. Such as the height of the frame where the material to be put into the container needs to be adjusted to the height of the wearer's arm in a standing position. The results of anthropometric measurements of users/research subjects are as follows.

Table 1. Anthropometric Data of Research Subjects

No	Size Name	Mini- mum	Max- mum	Rata- Rata	SD	Percentile		
						5	50	95
1	Standing height	161,27	177,12	167,87	5,21	161,37	167,88	176,97
2	Standing elbow height	95,17	117,40	105,32	5,70	95,22	105,31	117,10
3	Height of the stand reach	212,33	227,60	219,23	5,35	212,41	219,30	227,30
4	Seating height	145,24	167,30	156,20	5,62	145,31	156,30	166,97
5	Seated height	84,12	94,00	88,25	3,29	84,34	88,25	93,90
6	Sitting elbow height	19,72	29,10	25,18	3,40	19,79	25,19	28,90
7	Knee-high sitting	46,81	53,20	49,96	2,63	46,87	49,99	53,01
8	High <i>popliteal</i> seating	41,03	45,10	43,18	1,27	41,20	43,19	45,00
9	Shoulder length - elbow	32,10	39,10	36,17	2,45	32,12	36,18	39,03
10	Elbow length	44,12	49,20	46,25	2,12	44,20	46,29	48,97
11	Hand length	17,30	19,10	18,21	1,01	17,37	18,22	19,07
12	Hand width	10,11	11,50	10,56	1,29	10,13	10,51	11,49

Note: SD: Standard Deviation

Subject Workload Measurement

An employee's pulse is measured with a pulse meter both before and after work to determine their physical exertion. The following are the findings from the measurement of employee workload:

Table 2. Results of Subject's Pulse Calculation

Variable	Using your hands manually		Using the new tool (ergonomic flour mixer)		t	P
	Mean (bpm)	SD	Mean (bpm)	SD		
Resting pulse	75,29	3,47	76,34	3,92	6,137	0,184
Working pulse	125,13	5,29	106,22	6,12	4,142	0,000

Note: bpm: beats per minute; SD: Standard Deviation

Measurement of Musculoskeletal Disorders

Data on musculoskeletal ailments was gathered from respondents' responses to the Nordic Body Map survey. Questionnaires were presented to the subjects both before and after work. The following are the outcomes of measuring musculoskeletal diseases in employees:

Table 3. Results of Musculoskeletal Disorders Analysis

Variable	Using your hands manually		Using the new tool (ergonomic flour mixer)		t	P
	Average	SD	Average	SD		
Musculoskeletal Disorders before work	34,82	3,41	35,12	3,17	5,129	0,194
Musculoskeletal Disorders after work	78,42	5,19	40,86	4,27	7,021	0,000

Measurement of Work Fatigue

Data on job exhaustion among employees was acquired by means of the completion of thirty general fatigue questionnaire items. Questionnaires were presented to the subjects both before and after work. At this point, fatigue is still measured using outdated equipment. The following are the fatigue measurement results.

Table 4. Results of General Fatigue Analysis

Variable	Using your hands manually		Using the new tool (ergonomic flour mixer)		t	p
	Average	SD	Average	SD		
Fatigue Before Work	33,72	3,24	34,02	3,71	3,164	0,218
Fatigue after work	84,13	5,16	40,12	4,87	5,592	0,000

Measurement of Subject Work Productivity

The following formula is used to measure the productivity of the research subjects [6], [11]:

$$P = \frac{Op}{I \cdot t} \tag{1}$$

I is the input (average work pulse), t is the time (hours), Op is the output (the quantity of dough counted in an hour of work), and P is productivity.

This productivity calculation is still based on the manual use of old tools. Meanwhile, the calculation using the new design tool will be carried out at the end of July 2024. The results of the calculation of work productivity using the old tool are as follows:

Table 5. Work Productivity of Research Subjects

Variable	Using your hands manually		Using the new tool (ergonomic flour mixer)		t	p
	Average	SD	Average	SD		
Production Amount (kg/h)	32,81	5,18	167,28	4,18	3,471	0,000
Work productivity	0,262	0,021	1,575	0,102	2,687	0,000

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the flour dough mixer was to provide Tabanan Regency, Indonesia's MSMEs with a solution to their challenges. The manufacture of this flour dough machine is adjusted to the anthropometry of workers and in accordance with the principles of appropriate technology, namely easy to use, in accordance with the functions desired by the user, economical price, and environmentally friendly. this is in accordance with the wishes of workers or users (in accordance with the participatory principle) [12], [13], [14].

Table 1 shows the anthropometric data of the workers. This data is used to create the dimensions of the flour dough mixer machine. The height of the machine is adjusted to the height of the worker's elbow. The width of the machine is adjusted to the length of the worker's hand reach. The handle on the lid of the flour dough container is adjusted to the circumference of the worker's palm. The suitability of the machine dimensions to the worker's anthropometry is important so that the worker feels comfortable using the flour dough machine [15], [16], [17].

Table 2 shows that there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the design result and the resting pulse calculation results using the new tool and the old tool. This demonstrated that the workers' starting conditions were the same, indicating that the research intervention was unaffected by the workers' starting conditions. On the other hand, a noteworthy distinction was seen in the working pulse ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the use of an ergonomic flour dough mixer design affects workload. Prior to the intervention, the mean heart rate was recorded at 125.13 beats per minute, which encompasses elevated heart rates [3], [7]. Following the intervention, the workload (achieved through the use of an ergonomic flour dough mixer design) was found to be 106.22 beats per minute, or a moderate workload. A reduction of 15.1% in the workload from heavy to medium that is, from 125.13 beats per minute to 106.22 beats per minute can be reported.

Table 3 showed that there was no significant difference in the value of muscle complaints prior to work while utilising manual methods or outdated instruments ($p = 0.194$ or $p > 0.05$). "In the meantime, there is a significant difference with a value of $p = 0.000$ or $p < 0.05$ in musculoskeletal diseases following work. Based on the average score, there was a 47.9% drop in the musculoskeletal diseases score, from 78.42 to 40.86.

This finding is consistent with other studies by researchers who found that musculoskeletal diseases can be considerably reduced by ergonomic interventions that make use of suitable technology in the form of work aids [18], [19], [20], [21].

According to Table 4's work tiredness measurement data, there was no discernible difference in the workers' initial state of weariness before to work, with a p-value of 0.218 ($p > 0.05$). This demonstrates that while utilising the new ergonomic flour dough mixer design tool and the old tool, the workers' beginning conditions are the same. In the meantime, a significant difference with a value of $p = 0.000$ or $p < 0.05$ was found in the measuring of musculoskeletal diseases after work. Based on the average fatigue score, 84.13 was obtained while utilising traditional methods or outdated tools. In contrast, an ergonomic flour dough mixer resulted in a fatigue score of 40.12, which represents a 52.3% drop.

Kroemer and Grandjean stated [3] that ergonomic treatments are required for employees in order to address work-related issues that result in body aches and weariness as well as a drop in productivity. According to earlier research, ergonomic treatments, such as the use of work aids, can greatly reduce job tiredness and improve workers' ability to work efficiently, safely, and comfortably. The results of this study are consistent with that research. [22], [23], [24].

There is a substantial difference in the amount of production and work productivity ($p < 0.05$), as can be shown based on the computation of production outcomes and work productivity as indicated in Table 5. There was a 409.8% increase in dough mixing production, going from 32.81 kg/h to 167.28 kg/h. Concurrently, there was a 501.1% rise in work productivity, which went from 0.262 to 1.575.

The employment of an ergonomic flour dough mixer is the cause of the rise in output and productivity at work. While stirring with an ergonomic flour mixer speeds up and improves the effectiveness of the stirring process, the traditional way of combining flour dough takes a long time and strains the arms and hands. One of the ergonomic concepts is using assistive gadgets to do tasks [3], [7], [25]. To ensure that labour is done safely and comfortably, workers' tools must be tailored to their anthropometric size. Because small industries often struggle with finding the right balance between ideal output levels and worker productivity, increasing productivity in these sectors is imperative [4], [23], [26].

CONCLUSION

The following is the study's conclusion based on the findings and discussion above:

1. The anthropometric dimensions of the worker are taken into consideration when designing the ergonomic flour dough mixer. The tool's height measurement matches the height of the worker's standing elbow, and the container's dimension matches the worker's hand's reach.
2. The ergonomic design of the flour dough mixer can reduce the workload of MSME employees by 15.1%.
3. The ergonomic flour dough mixer design can reduce skeletal muscle complaints of MSME employees by 47.9%.
4. The design of the ergonomic flour dough mixer can reduce the fatigue of MSME employees by 52.3%.
5. The ergonomic flour dough mixer design can increase the work productivity of MSME employees by 501.1%.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in the research and creation of this article.

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